

The Determinants of Personality Formation of Public Services in the Local Government of Pohuwato Regency, Gorontalo

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Abstract: *The objective of the current study is to find out and analyze the determinants of personality formation of public services in the local government of Pohuwato regency. The method used in this study is a mix-method that is a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. The results showed that based on the results of the above analysis, it is concluded that the following matters, the determinants of personality formation of public services in the regional government of Pohuwato regency amounted to 79.90 after being confirmed by the Service Quality Score Interval Criteria table at a position with the value of 76.61-88.30, thus, the level of community satisfaction gets a good category while the Public Service implemented by the Pohuwato Regency Government is included in the category of service quality with the good category as well. Based on the results of this analysis, some of the suggestions in this study include: 1) service requirements still need to be improved, especially the service information to be easily seen, speed up time and service procedures and providing the training for implementers through training and career development. 2) repair the facilities and infrastructure for the convenience of customers and facilities for people with disabilities.*

Keywords: *Personality formation; Public Service; Local Government.*

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1. Background of the Study

In the era of personality formation of public service reform, it has become an inevitable demand. According to Law No. 25 of 2009, public services are activities or series in order to fulfill service needs in accordance with the laws and regulations for every citizen and resident for administrative goods, services and/or services provided by public organizers. The government as a public organizer has the function of providing services to the community, with demands to prioritize the interests of the community, simplify community affairs, shorten the process of implementing community affairs and even give satisfaction to the community.

To further examine the psychological aspects of personality formation in public service can be seen from the perspective of the world view concept, images of self and lifestyle which refers to the approach taken by Joseph Royce and Arnold Powell (1983). The concept can provide a complete, detailed and comprehensive picture of the psychological aspects that shape an individual's personality in terms of cognitive, affective, belief, value and integration of all these factors, thus leading to overt and tangible forms of behavior towards formation of personality in public service.

Therefore, the personality formation in services is highly demanded attention and handling for all stakeholders because it is a duty and function that is inherent in every village and sub-district apparatus in particular that the basis is the front line of public service providers. The quality of public services has a very broad impact, especially in relation to the level of community welfare. For this reason, efforts to improve public services need to be carried out continuously and continuously and must be carried out together, programmed, and consistent with regard to the needs and expectations of the community.

Since 2010 the Indonesian Government has implemented a national bureaucratic reform program. Until now the implementation of national bureaucratic reform has entered the second phase, which is marked by the compilation of the 2015-2019 Bureaucratic Reform Map through PERMENPAN No. 11 of 2015. In the Road Map, there were 3 (three) targets and 8 (eight) areas of change for 2015-2019 Bureaucratic Reform. The three targets are High-performance government, effective and efficient government, and quality public services.

These three targets become zones that have been agreed upon in the fact of integrity both by K/L/province/regency/city whose leaders and all

staff has the intention (commitment) to realize a clean and serviceable bureaucracy. To prove that every government institution both central and local has done good service, of course, a community satisfaction survey is needed. For this reason, PERMENPAN RB No. 14 of 2017 has issued a Guideline on the Community Satisfaction Index Survey, with the hope that every government institution from the center to the regions conducts a survey of services to determine the extent of community satisfaction with the performance of government apparatus in the formation personality towards society.

In Pohuwato Regency in terms of carrying out the personality formation of the public services so far, there has been no specific study related on this topic, thus public services, in general, are still a government monopoly, so there is no significant data to determine the extent of community satisfaction.

Based on the above problems, the research is carried out with the title **“The Determinants of Personality Formation of Public Services in the Local Government of Pohuwato Regency, Gorontalo”**

2. Research Problem

The formulations of the problem in this study are as follows: How the determinants of the personality formation of public services conducted through the survey of the community satisfaction index in the local government of Pohuwato Regency.

3. Research Objective

The objective of this study is described as follows: To find out and analyze the determinants of the personality formation of public services conducted through the survey of the community satisfaction index in the local government of Pohuwato Regency.

4. Theoretical basis

The Importance of Personality Formation in the Public Services

The formation of personality in service is highly demanded attention and handling for all stakeholders, because it is the duty and function inherent in every village and sub-district apparatus in particular that it is based on the forefront of public service providers. Moreover, the impact of public service quality is very broad, especially in relation to the level of community welfare. For this reason, efforts to improve public service need

to be carried out continuously and must be carried out together, programmed, and consistent with regard to the needs and expectations of the community.

To further examine the psychological aspects of personality formation in public service can be seen from the perspective of the world view concept, images of self and lifestyle which refers to the approach taken by Joseph R. Royce and Arnold Powell (1983). The concept can provide a complete, detailed and comprehensive picture of the psychological aspects that shape an individual's personality in terms of cognitive, affective, belief, value and integration of all these factors, therefore, it is leading to overt and tangible forms of behavior towards formation of personality in public service

Concept of Public Service

Understanding Public Services

In the life of nation and state service becomes an important thing because it involves the needs of the community which is an object that must be serviced and becomes the government's main task in terms of the public. Public services can be interpreted as providing services (serving) the needs of people or communities who have an interest in the organization in accordance with the basic rules and procedures that have been set. Many notions of public service are interpreted by experts, among others: Moenir (2001, p.13) Public service is an activity carried out by a person or group of people on the basis of material factors through systems, procedures and certain methods in an effort to meet the interests of others in accordance with their rights. The purpose of public services is to prepare for public services that are desired or needed by the public, and how to properly state the public about their choices and how to access them which are planned and provided by the government. Furthermore, according to Moenir (2001, p.13), public services must contain basic elements as follows: 1) The rights and obligations of the giver and the public service must be clear and clearly known by each party; 2) The regulation of each form of public service must be adjusted to the conditions of the need and the ability of the community to pay based on the applicable legal provisions while adhering to efficiency and effectiveness; 3) Quality, process and results of public services must be sought in order to provide accountability, comfort, legal certainty that can be accounted for; 4) If the public services held by the government are forced to be expensive, then the relevant government agencies are obliged to provide opportunities for the community to participate in organizing.

According to Thoha (Widodo, 2001), Professional public service means that public services are characterized by the existence of accountability and responsibility from service providers (government apparatus), with the following characteristics: 1. Effective, prioritizing the achievement of what is the goal and target; 2. Simple, meaning the procedures for services are held easily, quickly, precisely, not convoluted, easy to understand and easily implemented by the community requesting service; 3. Clarity and certainty (transparent) contain the meaning of clarity and certainty; 4. Openness, meaning procedures for the requirements of the work unit/official responsible for the service provider, time of completion, details of time/tariff and other matters relating to the service process must be informed openly so that it is easily known and understood by the community, both requested or not requested; 5. Efficiency; 6. Accuracy, time, these criteria mean that the implementation of community services can be completed within a predetermined period of time; 7. Responsive, more directed at responsiveness and quickly responding to the problems, needs and aspirations of the people served; 8. Adaptive, quickly resolve what is being demanded, the desires and aspirations of the people served who always experience growth and development. Other opinions that match the dimensions or measures of service quality are proposed by Fandy Tjiptono (1997, p.14) in his book *The Principles of Total Quality Service*, namely:

- Tangibles, including physical facilities, equipment, employees, and means of communication;
- Reliability, namely the ability to provide promised services promptly, accurately and satisfactorily;
- Responsiveness, which is the desire of staff to help customers and provide responsive service;
- Assurance, including knowledge, ability, politeness, and can be trusted by the staff; free from danger, risk or doubt;
- Empathy, includes the ease of making good communication relationships, personal attention, and understanding the needs of customers.

Public Service Objectives

The purpose of public services, in general, is how to prepare for public services that are desired or needed by the public, and how to properly state the public about their choices and how to access them planned and provided by the government (Zeithaml, Parasuraman & Berry, 1990).

Zeithaml further said the objectives of public services are as follows:

- Determine the services provided, what are the types;
- Treat service users, as customers;

- Trying to satisfy service users, according to what they want;
- Looking for ways to deliver the best and quality services;
- Provide ways, if the service user has no choice. (Zeithml et.al., 1990)

Public Service Standards

According to the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment Decree No. 63 of 2003 concerning General Guidelines for the Implementation of Public Services, service standards must include:

- Service Procedure, Service procedures carried out in this section include simplicity, namely the ease of providing services to the community as well as the ease of meeting service requirements.

- Time, Time Settlement determined from the time of filing the application with the completion of the service including complaints must be related to the certainty of time in providing services in accordance with the stipulation of the length of service each time.

- Service Fee. The service fee or tariff including the details specified in the service delivery process must be related to the imposition of fees that are reasonable and detailed and do not violate the existing provisions.

- Service Products. The results of services received are in accordance with the stipulated conditions. This is related to the reality in the provision of services, namely the results of service in accordance with the specified and free from technical errors, both in terms of writing applications that have been submitted previously.

- Facilities and infrastructure. Provision of adequate facilities and infrastructure by public service providers. This is related to the availability of adequate supporting devices such as tables, chairs, typewriters, etc. And there is comfort and convenience in obtaining service.

Thus public services are all service activities carried out by public service providers as an effort to fulfill public needs and the implementation of the provisions of the legislation. The implementation of the implementation of public services, the Government apparatus is responsible for providing the best service to the community in order for creating prosperity. The community has the right to get the best service from the government because the community has provided funds in the form of payment of taxes, levies, and various other levies. In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services, that the community has the right to obtain quality services in accordance with the principles and objectives of the service. The main purpose of public service is community satisfaction.

Community satisfaction can be realized if the services provided are in accordance with service standards or are already better than the prescribed service standards. Therefore, the method used to measure community satisfaction and the quality of services provided is to use the community satisfaction index contained in the Minister of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Regulation Number 14 of 2017 concerning Guidelines for Community Satisfaction Survey Service Units of Government Agencies. Quality is a dynamic condition that affects products, services, people, processes and environments that meet or exceed expectations (Tjiptono, 2001). Service quality can be interpreted as an effort to fulfill the needs and desires of consumers as well as the accuracy of delivery in offsetting consumer expectations (Tjiptono, 2007). Service quality can be known by comparing the public perception of the real services received/obtained by the services that the community actually hopes for the service attributes. If the service received or perceived (perceived service) is as expected, then the quality of service is perceived as good and satisfying, if the service received exceeds consumer expectations, then the quality of service is perceived as very good and quality. Conversely, if the services received are lower than expected, then the quality of service is perceived poorly.

The community satisfaction index is data and information about the level of community satisfaction obtained from the results of quantitative and qualitative measurements of community opinion in obtaining services from public service providers by comparing expectations and needs. Pohuwato Regency Government is one of the government agencies that conduct public services. Various types of licensing services are given. The service is the author for several clusters. Based on the initial observations that have been made there are problems encountered in the service section. The quality of services provided is also influenced by the service facilities provided. Therefore, service facilities for the community are things that must be considered by service providers. Service facilities need such as the lack of computers used by the community to fill out community satisfaction surveys and seating in the waiting room is still lacking. Another factor that causes a lack of community satisfaction is that the officers are less friendly, there is no certainty of time and the information costs charged to the community in managing the permits are not detailed yet the scheme/plot that describe the procedure for the process of available queuing tools for visitors. This condition shows that the organizers of public services are still faced with a system of government that has not been effective and efficient and the quality of the human resources of the apparatus is inadequate.

5. Research Methodology

Research Locus and Research Time

To obtain accurate data about public services in the Pohuwato Regency Government, then the OPD was established which became a research locus, among others

- Governance Group with a sample of the Dukcapil Service and the Marisa Sub-District Office in Pohuwato District
- Health Cluster with a sample of Pohuwato District Hospital Service
- Human resources cluster with samples of Pohuwato District Education Office
- Economic Cluster with samples of the Office of Action, Fisheries and Investment in Pohuwato Regency
- Infra-structure Clump with a sample of PUPR Service, Disporatar Service, and PDAM of Pohuwato District

In order to obtain more valid data, in-depth interviews were conducted with 150 respondents. Time of implementation for 3 (three) months, from July to September 2018

Research methods

The research method used in this research is a mix-method, which is a combination of qualitative methods and quantitative methods with measurements using a Likert Scale.

Data analysis

Analysis of data on the Community Satisfaction Survey based on RB Permenpan No. 14 of 2017 concerning Guidelines for Preparing the Public Satisfaction Survey for the Public Service Delivery Unit as shown below.

Table 1. Service Quality Score Interval Criteria

Perception Value	Interval value (NI)	Interval Conversion Value (NIK)	Service quality	Unit performance
1	1,00-2,5996	25,00 – 64,99	D	Bad
2	2,60 – 3,064	65,00 – 76,60	C	Almost Good
3	3,0644 – 3,532	76,61 – 88,30	B	Good
4	3,5324 – 4,00	88,31 – 100,00	A	Very good

Data sources: RB *Permenpan* No. 14 of 2017

6. Research and Discussion Results

Research Results

Pohuwato Regency is one of the Regencies in Gorontalo Province. The district is the farthest district from the center of the capital. It is located from the center of the provincial capital of approximately 200 km. Gorontalo Regency has 13 sub-districts and 104 villages and sub-districts. This district has an area of 4,244.31km² and population: 141,281 (Source of DKCS 2018). To get accurate data on research on public services and community satisfaction in the Pohuwato District Government, researchers circulated 50 questionnaires (50 respondents). From the whole questionnaire distributed to OPD in Pohuwato regency as the research samples.

To obtain accurate data about public services in the Pohuwato Regency Government, then the OPD was established which became a research locus, for the example

- Governance Group with samples of the Dukcapil Office, the Investment Office and the Marisa Sub-District Office in Pohuwato Regency
- Health Cluster with a sample of the Regional Public Hospital Service (RSUD) of Pohuwato Regency
- HR cluster with samples of Pohuwato District Education Office
- Economic Clump with samples of the Office of Action and Fisheries Services of the Pohuwato District
- Infra-structure Clump with a sample of PUPR Service, Disporatar Service and Pohuwato District PDAM.

From the results of data processing of each OPD in Pohuwato Regency, results are obtained as in table 2.

Table 2. Results of the IKM Survey in Pohuwato District in 2018

NO	SURVEYED OPD	QUESTIONS IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE									Average	Service Quality	Category
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9			
A 1	Government Aspect												
	<i>Dukcapil</i>												
	Performance	3,36	3,22	3,08	3,9	3,16	3,1	3,34	3,2	3,34	3,30	82,50	B
	Hopes	3,92	3,94	3,84	4,00	3,96	4,00	4,00	3,92	4,00	3,95		
GAP	-0,56	-0,72	-0,76	-0,10	-0,80	-0,90	-0,66	-0,72	-0,66	-0,65			
2	Investment Office												
	Performance	3,36	3,40	2,88	3,04	3,46	2,96	3,28	2,92	3,34	3,18	79,56	B

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	Hopes	4,00	3,98	3,84	4,00	4,00	3,88	4,00	3,84	3,96	3,94		
	GAP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
3	Marisa District	0,64	0,58	0,96	0,96	0,54	0,92	0,72	0,92	0,62			
	Performance	3,18	3,12	2,80	3,00	3,24	2,94	3,24	2,90	3,16	3,06	76,61	B
	Hopes	3,94	3,80	3,80	4,00	3,90	3,90	4,00	3,80	3,96	3,90		
	GAP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0,84		
B	Health Aspect												
4	Hospital												
	Performance	3,24	3,14	3,04	3,36	3,22	3,46	3,38	3,26	3,38	3,28	81,89	B
	Hopes	3,92	3,86	3,74	3,88	3,98	3,96	4,00	3,92	4,00	3,92		
	GAP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0,64		
C	Human Resources Aspect												
5	Educational office												
	Performance	3,14	3,30	2,80	3,90	3,28	3,64	3,18	2,78	3,24	3,25	81,28	B
	Hopes	3,96	3,96	3,74	4,00	3,94	4,00	4,00	3,78	3,94	3,92		
	GAP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0,67		
D	Economics Aspect												
6	<i>Perindagkeop</i>												
	Performance	3,24	3,28	2,98	3,22	3,00	3,16	3,30	3,04	3,16	3,15	78,83	B
	Hopes	4,00	4,00	3,80	3,98	3,82	4,00	3,86	3,82	4,00	3,92		
	GAP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0,77		
7	Fishery Affairs												
	Performance	3,20	3,30	3,04	3,22	3,16	3,10	3,36	3,12	3,00	3,17	79,17	B
	Hopes	4,00	4,00	3,84	4,00	3,94	4,00	3,86	3,90	3,86	3,93		
	GAP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0,77		
E	Infrastructure Aspect												
8	<i>PU PR</i>												
	Performance	3,12	3,22	2,92	3,08	3,10	3,12	3,06	3,22	2,96	3,09	77,22	B
	Hopes	4,00	4,00	3,88	3,98	4,00	3,96	3,84	3,94	3,96	3,95		
	GAP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0,86		
9	<i>Disporapar</i>												
	Performance	3,20	3,14	2,66	3,04	3,18	2,98	3,24	2,90	2,92	3,03	75,72	C
	Hopes	3,96	3,82	3,66	4,00	3,90	3,92	4,00	3,80	3,82	3,88		

10	GAP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0,85		
	<i>PDAM</i>												
	Performance	3,28	3,16	2,98	2,88	3,12	3,10	3,14	3,04	2,98	3,08	76,89	B
	Hope	4,00	4,00	3,96	3,88	4,00	3,98	3,84	3,98	3,98	3,96		
	GAP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0,88		
	Amount of performance	32,32	32,28	29,18	32,64	31,92	31,56	32,52	30,38	31,48	28,40	78,90	B
	Average of performance	3,23	3,23	2,92	3,26	3,19	3,16	3,25	3,04	3,15	3,16		
	Amount of hopes	39,70	39,36	38,10	39,72	39,44	39,60	39,40	38,70	39,48	35,33	98,15	A
	Average of hopes	3,97	3,94	3,81	3,97	3,94	3,96	3,94	3,87	3,95	3,93		

Discussion

Based on the survey results in table 2. above, the author can describe the discussion as follows:

OPD Governance Group within the Pohuwato District Government

IKM Data Analysis at the District Population and Civil Registry (Dispenduk of Civil Registration) Pohuwato

Based on Table 2, it shows that in general, the people who came to Dispenduk Capil judged both the Public services provided. Where there is an average interval of 3.28 or the average conversion interval of 82.50 while the gap value (GAP) between the performance and expectations of the average community is obtained at -0.65.

Furthermore, in this survey there are 3 (three) types of public service elements that have a satisfaction index below the average that requires serious treatment from Dispenduk of civil registry, namely:

- The speed of time in providing services;
- Officer competency in service;
- The suitability of the intermediate service products listed in the service standard with the results provided.

The alternative solutions to the problem are as follows:

- The need for socialization to the public is held on the importance of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM) survey in an effort to improve the quality of services to realize excellent service (public service) in the sense

of meeting the expectations and needs of both the providers and recipients of services.

- The consistency of public service providers in all sectors is needed to continuously improve their capabilities, skills, comfort, security, and supporting infrastructure facilities and are willing and able to carry out public services in a transparent and accountable manner.

- The need to increase apparatus human resources through seminars, training, and technical training on public services in an effort to support the implementation of the IKM survey.

IKM Data Analysis at the Marisa Sub-District Office in Pohuwato District

Based on Table 2.2 shows that in general, the people who came to the Marisa Sub-District Office judged well on the public services provided. Where there is an average interval of 3.06 or the average conversion interval of 76.61 while the gap value (GAP) between the performance and expectations of the average community is obtained at -0.84.

Furthermore, in this survey there are 3 (three) types of public service elements that have a satisfaction index below the average that requires serious handling from the Sub-District Office of Marisa, namely:

- The speed of time in providing service,
- The quality of facilities used
- The officer competency in service.

Solution to problem

Based on the analysis of the problem, the alternative solutions to the problem are as follows:

- The need for socialization to the public is held on the importance of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM) survey in an effort to improve the quality of services to realize excellent service (public service) in the sense of meeting the expectations and needs of both the providers and recipients of services.

- The consistency of public service providers in all sectors is needed to continuously improve their capabilities, skills, comfort, security, and supporting infrastructure facilities and are willing and able to carry out public services in a transparent and accountable manner.

- The need to increase apparatus human resources through seminars, training, and technical training on public services in an effort to support the implementation of the IKM survey.

Health Aspect in Pohuwato Regency Government

IKM Data Analysis at the OPD of the Pohuwato Regional Public Sakita House

In accordance with Table 2.2 shows that in general, the people who came to the RSUD assessed both the public services provided. Where there is a value the average interval is 3.28 or the average conversion interval is 81.89 while the gap value (GAP) between the performance and expectations of the average community is -0.64.

The following are some of the things complained by the community that was netted during in-depth interviews, both interviews directly and through telephone lines, as follows:

- Administrative requirements and distribution of study assistance require considerable time and exceed the limits of school funding/needs payments;

- The time for processing old documents and not according to the time of completion of the document submitted by the officer, as stated by several respondents that for the time to administer poor scholarship assistance/end of study can be more than 1 month Service Time even to the end of the tuition fee payment requirement.

- Officers are less friendly in providing services such as not greeting the respondent and lacking a smile when giving services and often not found officers in the public service area.

- Officers are not dexterous in serving and are unable to provide information regarding progress in completing the Service Competency document

- According to a number of respondents stating that the procedure for poor management of study assistance/scholarships must go back and forth to procedure hospitals.

- Queues are not disciplined/irregular. Some residents complained that often the latter arrived instead served first then those who had already been in line.

- The waiting room is not provided with refrigeration so that people often overheat and go in and out to find fresh air outside.

Solution to problem

Based on the analysis of the problems mentioned above, the alternative solutions to the problem are as follows:

- The need for socialization to the public is held about the importance of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM) survey in an effort

to improve the quality of services to create excellent service (public service) in the sense meet the expectations and needs of both the giver and recipient of the service.

- The consistency of public service providers in all sectors is needed to continuously improve their capabilities, skills, comfort, security, and supporting infrastructure facilities and are willing and able to carry out public services in a transparent and accountable manner.

- The need to increase apparatus human resources through seminars, training, and technical training on public services in an effort to support the implementation of the IKM survey.

Human Resources Aspect in Pohuwato Regency Regional Government

IKM Data Analysis at the Education Office OPD in Pohuwato District.

Graph 2.4 shows that in general, the people who came to the Education Office assessed that the public services provided were good. Where there is an average interval of 3.28 or the average conversion interval of 81.28 while the gap value (GAP) between the performance and expectations of the average community is obtained at -0.68.

The following are some of the things complained by the community that was netted during in-depth interviews, both interviews directly and through telephone lines, as follows:

- Administrative requirements and distribution of study assistance require considerable time and exceed the limits of school funding/needs payments;

- The time for processing old documents and not according to the time of completion of the document submitted by the officer, as stated by several respondents that for the time to take care of poor scholarship/end of study can be more than 1 month service time even to the end of tuition fee payment requirements in college .

- Officers are less friendly in providing services such as not responding to respondents and lacking a smile when giving services and often not found officers in public services.

- Officers are not dexterous in serving and are unable to provide information regarding progress in completing the Service Competency document

- According to a number of respondents stating procedures for management poor study assistance/scholarship achievements must go back and forth to the Office of Education procedures.

- Queues are not disciplined / irregular. Some residents complained that often the latter arrived instead served first then those who had already been in line.

- The waiting room is not provided with refrigeration so that people often overheat and go in and out to find fresh air outside.

Solution to problem

Based on the analysis of the problems mentioned above, the alternative solutions to the problem are as follows:

- The need for socialization to the public is held on the importance of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM) survey in an effort to improve the quality of services to realize excellent service (public service) in the sense of meeting the expectations and needs of both the providers and recipients of services.

- The consistency of public service providers in all sectors is needed to continuously improve their capabilities, skills, comfort, security, and supporting infrastructure facilities and are willing and able to carry out public services in a transparent and accountable manner.

- The need to increase apparatus human resources through seminars, training, and technical training on public services in an effort to support the implementation of the IKM survey.

Economic Aspect in Pohuwato Regency Regional Government

IKM Data Analysis on the OPD of the Pohuwato District Investment Office

In Graph 2.5 above, the average value of the performance interval is 3.36 or the conversion average value is 84.00. Then the performance elements of service requirements in the Investment Office are included in the "Good" category. However, the gap value or GAP value between service performance and community expectations is -0.64. This means that there is still hope for the community that has not been fulfilled and requires the attention of organizers at the Investment Office.

Based on the description above there are 3 (three) types of public service elements that have a satisfaction index below the average that requires serious handling from the Investment Office, namely:

- The speed of time in providing services;
- Quality of Facilities and Infrastructure
- Competency/ability of officers in service.

Solution to problem

Based on the analysis of the problems mentioned above, the alternative solutions to the problem are as follows:

- The need for socialization to the public is held on the importance of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM) survey in an effort to improve the quality of services to realize excellent service (public service) in the sense of meeting the expectations and needs of both the providers and recipients of services.

- The consistency of public service providers in all sectors is needed to continuously improve their capabilities, skills, comfort, security, and supporting infrastructure facilities and are willing and able to carry out public services in a transparent and accountable manner.

- The need to increase apparatus human resources through seminars, training, and technical training on public services in an effort to support the implementation of the IKM survey.

IKM Data Analysis on the OPD of the Office of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives and Small Business in Pohuwato Regency

Graph 2.6, the average value of the performance interval is 3.24 or the average conversion value is 81.00. Then the elemental performance of service requirements in the Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives, and Small Business is included in the "Good" category. Although this element, according to the community, is good, there is still a gap or GAP value between official performance and community expectations of -0.78. This means that there is still hope for the community that has not been fulfilled and requires the attention of government officials in the Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives, and Small Businesses.

Based on the description above there are 3 (three) types of public service elements that have a satisfaction index below the average that requires serious handling from the Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives, and Small Businesses namely:

- The speed of time in providing services;
- Conformity between intermediate service products listed in service standards with the results given;
- Quality of Facilities and Infrastructure

Solution to problem

Based on the analysis of the problems mentioned above, the alternative solutions to the problem are as follows:

- The need for socialization to the public is held on the importance of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM) survey in an effort to improve the quality of services to realize excellent service (public service) in the sense of meeting the expectations and needs of both the providers and recipients of services.

- The consistency of public service providers in all sectors is needed to continuously improve their capabilities, skills, comfort, security, and supporting infrastructure facilities and are willing and able to carry out public services in a transparent and accountable manner.

- The need to increase apparatus human resources through seminars, training, and technical training on public services in an effort to support the implementation of the IKM survey.

IKM Data Analysis at the Pohuwato District Fisheries Department OPD

Graph 2. shows that in general, the people who came to the Fisheries Service assessed the public services provided. Where there is an average interval of 3.17 or the average conversion interval of 71.107 while the gap value (GAP) between the performance and expectations of the average community is obtained at -0.77.

Furthermore, in this survey there are 3 (three) types of public service elements that have a satisfaction index below the average that requires serious handling from the Fisheries Service, namely:

- Handling complaints of service users
- The speed of time in providing services;
- Officer competency in service;

Solution to problem

Based on the analysis of the problem, the alternative solutions to the problem are as follows:

- The need for socialization to the public is held on the importance of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM) survey in an effort to improve the quality of services to realize excellent service (public service) in the sense of meeting the expectations and needs of both the providers and recipients of services.

- The consistency of public service providers in all sectors is needed to continuously improve their capabilities, skills, comfort, security, and supporting infrastructure facilities and are willing and able to carry out public services in a transparent and accountable manner.

- The need to increase apparatus human resources through seminars, training, and technical training on public services in an effort to support the implementation of the IKM survey.

Infra Clump Structure in the Pohuwato Regency Government environment

IKM Data Analysis on OPD Public Works and Spatial Planning (PUPR)

Based on Graph 2.8 shows that in general, the people who came to the Public Works Agency and PR assessed both the public services provided. Where there is an average interval value of 3.09 or the average conversion interval value of 77.22 while the gap value (GAP) between the performance and expectations of the average community is obtained at - 0.86.

Furthermore, in this survey, there are 3 (three) types of public service elements that have a satisfaction index below the average that requires serious handling from the Public Works and Public Relations Agency, namely:

- The speed of time in providing services;
- Handling complaints of service users
- The behavior of officers in services related to courtesy and friendliness

Solution to problem

- The need for socialization to the public is held on the importance of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM) survey in an effort to improve the quality of services to realize excellent service (public service) in the sense of meeting the expectations and needs of both the providers and recipients of services.

- The consistency of public service providers in all sectors is needed to continuously improve its capabilities, skills, comfort, security, and supporting infrastructure facilities and willing and able to carry out public services in a transparent and accountable manner.

- The need to increase apparatus human resources through seminars, training, and technical training on public services in an effort to support the implementation of the IKM survey.

IKM Data Analysis on the OPD of the Tirta Maleo Regional Water Company (PDAM)

Graph 2.9 shows the average value of the performance interval of 3.28 or the average conversion value of 82.00. So the performance elements of service requirements at PDAM Tirta Maleo are included in the "Good" category. Although this element, according to the community, is good, however, there is still a large gap value or GAP value between service performance and community expectations of -0.72. This means that there are still many expectations of the community that have not been fulfilled in the element of conformity with the type of service.

Furthermore, in this survey there are 3 (three) types of public service elements that have a satisfaction index below the average that requires serious handling of PDAM Tirta Maleo, namely:

- Fairness of rates/costs in service
- Handling complaints of service users
- The speed of time in providing services;

Solution to problem

Based on the analysis of the problems mentioned above, the alternative solutions to the problem are as follows:

- The need for socialization to the public is held on the importance of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM) survey in an effort to improve the quality of services to realize excellent service (public service) in the sense of meeting the expectations and needs of both the providers and recipients of services.

- The consistency of public service providers in all sectors is needed to continuously improve their capabilities, skills, comfort, security, and supporting infrastructure facilities and are willing and able to carry out public services in a transparent and accountable manner.

- The need to increase the human resources of the apparatus through seminars, training, and technical training on public services in an effort to support the implementation of the IKM survey.

IKM Data Analysis on DPOs in the Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism (Disporapar)

Based on Graph 2.10, it shows that in general, the people who come to the Department of Youth, Sports, and Tourism assess both the public services provided. Where there is an average interval of 3.03 or the average conversion interval value of 75.72 while the gap value (GAP) between the

performance and expectations of the average community is obtained at - 0.85.

Furthermore, in this survey, there are 3 (three) types of public service elements that have a satisfaction index below the average that requires serious handling from the Department of Youth, Sports, and Tourism, namely: Speed of time in providing services; Quality of facilities and infrastructure; Handling complaints of service users.

Problem Solving

Based on the analysis of the problems mentioned above, the alternative solutions to the problem are as follows:

- The need for socialization to the public is held on the importance of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM) survey in an effort to improve the quality of services to realize excellent service (public service) in the sense of meeting the expectations and needs of both the providers and recipients of services.

- The consistency of public service providers in all sectors is needed to continuously improve their capabilities, skills, comfort, security, and supporting infrastructure facilities and are willing and able to carry out public services in a transparent and accountable manner.

- The need to increase apparatus human resources through seminars, training, and technical training on public services in an effort to support the implementation of the IKM survey.

7. Conclusions and Suggestions

Conclusions

Based on the results of the above analysis, it is concluded the following matter:

- The determinants of personality formation for public services conducted through the survey of the community satisfaction index in the Government of Pohuwato Regency is at a value of 79.90 after being confirmed by the Service Quality Interval Criteria table at a value position between 76.61-88.30 thus the level of community satisfaction obtains the Good category

Suggestions

Based on the results of the analysis above, some of the suggestions in this study include:

- Service requirements still need to be improved, especially information to be easy, speed up time and service procedures and provide training for implementers through training and career development.
- Repair the facilities and infrastructure for consumer comfort and facilities for people with disabilities.

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